

PREPARATION AND PROPERTIES OF CERAMIC MATRIX COMPOSITES WITH TYRANNO FIBERSTM AS THE REINFORCEMENT

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SUMMARY: In order to up-grade high temperature properties of SiC^F/SiC composites, SiC-based fibers as the reinforcement, precursor polymers for the SiC-based matrix and the fiber/matrix interfacial structure were investigated. The crystallized Si-Al-C fiber (Tyranno-SA) was very useful reinforcement for the excellent mechanical properties of SiC^F/SiC composites at high temperature. It was found that the co-polymer of polymethylsilane (PMS) and polycarbosilane (PCS) was able to be converted to a near-stoichiometric SiC matrix. The addition of ZrSiO₄ particles into SiC-based matrix was improved the strength of SiC^F/SiC composite at high temperature in air, even the SiC-based matrix has included a lot of excess carbon. Tyranno-ZMI-S6^F/C/SiC composite, which had the carbon-rich SiC interphase, exhibited about 400MPa of tensile strength at 1673K in air. Below 1600K in air for short time, SiC^F/SiC composites with h-BN interphase were good mechanical properties.

KEYWORDS: fiber-reinforced composite, silicon carbide matrix, silicon carbide fiber, BN interphase, ZrSiO₄ interphase, particle-dispersed matrix, ZrSiO₄ particle

INTRODUCTION

Ceramic matrix composites (CMC) with fine silicon carbide fibers, which are NicalonTM, TyrannoTM fiber, etc., as the reinforcement are promised for the thermostructural materials, and recent advancement in these type of CMC concerning with heat resistance and oxidation resistance at high temperatures has also been demonstrated by use of crystallized Hi-Nicalon type-STM or SylramicTM fibers with the near-stoichiometric C/Si atomic ratio as the reinforcing material instead of NicalonTM and Hi-NicalonTM.

Tyranno fiber, which is SiC-based fiber with a little Ti or Zr, 8-11 μ m diameter, high mechanical strength and excellent heat resistance, has been produced from an organometallic polymer, polytitano(zircono)carbosilane, by pyrolysis of its spun fiber[1-3]. More recently, a new type Tyranno-SATM fiber, which is SiC-based crystallized fiber with a little Al, has been produced by changing the pyrolysis process of precursor polymer[4]. This Tyranno-SA fiber seems more suitable because of high creep property, excellent heat resistance and near-stoichiometric C/Si atomic ratio than ordinary Tyranno fibers.

SiC^F/SiC composites obtained by the chemical vapor infiltration (CVI) method have been widely studied comparing with other fabrication processes, such as polymer impregnation and

pyrolysis (PIP) method and reaction sintering method. However CVI method has disadvantages in cost and size limitation stand points.

For the purpose of developing the more attractive material than usual SiC^F/SiC composites for thermostructural materials, the compatibility of pyrolyzed materials obtained from polymethylsilane and polycarbosilane for the matrix and BN and ZrSiO₄ layer as fiber/matrix interphase of SiC^F/SiC composites has been tested. Furthermore the durability and cyclic fatigue characteristics of SiC^F/SiC composite, which prepared by PIP method using the polyzirconocarbosilane including oxide ceramic particles as the matrix precursor, have been investigated at high temperatures in air. The properties of these improved materials are presented in this paper.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

Preparation of SiC-based fibers

Polycarbosilane (PCS) was prepared by the rearrangement of polydimethylsilane at 550-725K in an inert atmosphere. Polymetalocarbosilane (PMC), which is the precursor polymer of Si-M-C-O fiber (Tyranno fibers, M:Ti, Zr or Al), was produced by the reaction of PCS with metal (Ti, Zr or Al) complex compound or alkoxide at a temperature over 525K in N₂ gas. Synthesized PMC was melt-spun into a continuous PMC fiber and cured by heat treatment in air. The cured PMC fibers was pyrolyzed continuously through the furnace up to 1700K in a N₂ gas stream, to obtained Si-M-C-O fibers[1-4]. And in the case of Si-Al-C fiber (Tyranno-SA fiber), the fiber structure made of near- stoichiometric polycrystalline SiC was obtained by heat treating Si-Al-C-O fiber at a temperature over 1900K in an Ar gas stream[4]. Table 1 shows the various properties of Si-Ti(Zr,Al)-C-O fibers, Tyranno-LoxM, -ZMI, -ZE and -SA. Tyranno-SA exhibits low tensile strength, compare to other Tyranno fibers, but had

Table 1: Properties of Tyranno fibers

Property		Si-Ti-C-O (LoxM)	Si-Zr-C-O (ZMI)	Si-Zr-C-O (ZE)	Si-Al-C (SA)
Fiber diameter	(μm)	11	11	13	10
Number of filaments	(Fil/yarn)	800	800	400	800
Tex	(g/1000m)	200	200	140	160
Tensile strength	(GPa)	3.3	3.4	3.5	2.8
Tensile modulus	(GPa)	187	200	233	420
Elongation	(%)	1.8	1.7	1.5	0.7
Density	(g/cm ³)	2.48	2.48	2.55	3.02
Specific heat	(J/gK)	0.735	0.709	0.712	0.669
Thermal	(W/mK)	1.35	2.52	3.78	64.6
Chemical	Si (mass%)	55.4	56.6	58.9	67.8
	C	32.4	34.8	38.4	31.3
	O	10.2	7.6	1.7	0.3
	Ti	2	-	-	-
	Zr	-	1	1	-
	Al	-	-	-	2
	C/Si(atomic)	1.37	1.44	1.48	1.08
Structure		amorphous	amorphous	amorphous	crystalline

(Tensile test; epoxy resin impregnated strand method)

excellent Young's modulus. Tyranno-ZE has included lots of excess carbon.

Synthesis and analysis of PMS polymer for SiC-based matrix

PMS was prepared from CH_3SiHCl by the dechlorination reaction in toluene solvent[5]. Synthesized PMS was analyzed by NMR using a JEOL JNM-EX400WB, and by FT-IR using a JASCO FT/IR-700. Next, PMS was pyrolyzed in electric furnace with a heating rate of 25K/h to 673K, 50K/h to 1273K in a N_2 gas, where they were kept for 2h. Because there is excess silicon in pyrolyzed PMS and excess carbon in pyrolyzed PCS, for the purpose of obtaining stoichiometric SiC-based matrix, mixture of PMS and PCS in various ratios were heat-treated in a N_2 gas and pyrolyzed in the same way.

Fig.1: Auger depth profile of Tyranno-ZMI heat-treated at 1823K in $\text{CO}+\text{CO}_2$ gas for 10.8ks.

Surface modification of SiC-based fibers

In order to obtain SiC/SiC composites with excellent mechanical properties, the surfaces of Tyranno fibers were modified by various techniques. Tyranno-ZMI fiber was heat-treated above 1600K in a mixture of CO and CO_2 gas; as a result the gradient structure with carbon was formed near the surface, as shown in Fig.1. The heat-treated Tyranno-ZMI fiber is called ZMI-S6 in this paper. Tyranno-SA, -ZE and -ZMI fiber were coated with BN at 1843K, 1763K and 1723K by CVD method with an NH_3 and a BCl_3 gas, respectively. From the results of X-ray diffraction measurement and a scanning electron microscope (SEM) observation, the coated BN layer was h-NB of about $0.3\mu\text{m}$ in thickness. Also Tyranno-ZMI fiber coated with ZrSiO_4 by sol-gel method, and then the coated fiber was heat-treated up to about 1100K in order to crystallization of ZrSiO_4 layer.

Process and evaluation of $\text{SiC}^{\text{F}}/\text{SiC}$ composite with surface-modified SiC-based fiber

The preparation process of single-tow $\text{SiC}^{\text{F}}/\text{SiC}$ composite shows in Fig.2. The single tow consisted of 400-800 filaments of BN-coated and ZrSiO_4 -coated Tyranno-SA, -ZE and -ZMI fibers was impregnated with polyzirconocarbosilane, and then pyrolyzed at about 1550K in an N_2 gas. The SiC-based matrix composites, which has been reinforced unidirectional with coated Tyranno fibers, were obtained by carrying out the impregnation and the pyrolysis to 2 times. These are hereafter denoted as the «Tyranno^F/interphase/matrix», for example, «SA^F/BN/SiC», «ZMI^F/ ZrSiO_4 /SiC», etc.. $\text{SiC}^{\text{F}}/\text{SiC}$ composite with the matrix including BaO-MgO- Al_2O_3 - SiO_2 glass-ceramics (BMAS) particles and ZrSiO_4 crystal particles was prepared by the same PIP method using polyzirconocarbosilane with 30mass% of BMAS and ZrSiO_4 as the matrix precursor, respectively. In this case, ZMI-S6 fiber was employed as the

Fig.2: The preparation process and evaluation conditions of single-tow $\text{SiC}^{\text{F}}/\text{SiC}$ composite.

reinforcement. These are hereafter denoted as the «ZMI- $\text{SiC}^{\text{F}}/\text{C}/\text{SiC} + \text{BMAS}$ » and «ZMI- $\text{SiC}^{\text{F}}/\text{C}/\text{SiC} + \text{ZrSiO}_4$ ».

The tensile test was performed for single-tow $\text{SiC}^{\text{F}}/\text{SiC}$ composites at 300-1700K in air.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Properties of PMSs as raw materials of SiC -based matrices

In this study, PMSs with high molecular weight were synthesized by conventional reflux method, not by the sonochemical synthesis method recently reported by Pawel Czubarow et al.[6].

Fig.3: FT-IR spectrum of synthesized PMS polymer.

Fig.4: ^1H -NMR spectrum of synthesized PMS polymer

Table 2: Chemical composition of pyrolyzed PMS

Si (mass%)	74.2
C	24.8
O	1.0
C/Si (atomic)	0.78

(Pyrolysis; at 1000°C for 1h in Ar)

Fig.5: Dependence on $\text{PMS}/(\text{PMS}+\text{PCS})$ of (a) yield and (b) C/Si atomic ratio.

accompanied by the usual PCS synthesis method. Fig.3 and 4 show the FT-IR spectrum and NMR spectrum of synthesized PMS, respectively. The bonding of Si-H, Si-CH₃, Si-C, Si-H₂, H-Si-CH₃ and Si-Si-CH₃ were recognized from these spectrum. In order to determine the

structural formula, the integrated intensity of signals about the Si-CH₃ bonding and the Si-H bonding were calculated from ¹H-NMR spectrum. It was estimated to be [(CH₃-SiH)_{0.5}-(CH₃-Si)_{0.5}]_n. Table 2 shows the composition after PMS was pyrolyzed at 1000°C in argon. There was excess silicon, so C/Si atomic ratio = 0.78. PMS and PCS mixed in various ratio were pyrolyzed at 1000°C in nitrogen to control the C/Si atomic ratio. Fig.5 (a), (b) show the yield and the C/Si atomic ratio after pyrolysis as a function of PMS/(PMS+PCS) weight ratio, respectively. The yield was proportional to the calculating value on the basis of the yield of PMS and PCS corresponding to 53.5% and 86.5%, respectively. On the other hand, the C/Si atomic ratio was proportional to the calculating value based on the C/Si atomic ratio of PMS and PCS coinciding with 0.79 and 1.45, respectively, and its ratio increased with a rise in the weight ratio of PCS. The C/Si atomic ratio showed a near-stoichiometric composition when PMS/(PMS+PCS) weight ratio was 0.7.

Mechanical properties of SiC^F/SiC composites with h-NB fiber/matrix interphase and ZrSiO₄ fiber/matrix interphase

The h-BN interphase is promised the interfacial structure for SiC^F/SiC composites with excellent oxidation resistance at high temperatures, instead of C interphase. Therefore, in this work, mechanical properties of Tyranno^F/BN/SiC were investigated at high temperatures in air. Fig.6 shows the tensile strength of Tyranno^F/BN/SiC at 300-1700K in air, together with that of usual Tyranno^F/C/SiC (TM-S6/C/SiC). From the observation by a transmission electron microscope (TEM), it was found that the carbon-rich SiC layer was formed at fiber/matrix interfacial region in TM-S6/C/SiC. Tyranno^F/BN/SiCs exhibited a excellent tensile strength relative to TM-S6/C/SiC with carbon-rich SiC interphase. In particular, SA^F/BN/SiC retained the tensile strength near to that at R.T. even at 1673K in air. The excellent thermal stability of the composite is attributable to the thermal stability of SA which is the reinforcement. The tensile strength of ZE^F/BN/SiC drastically decreased above 1600K. It seems that the decrease of tensile strength is due to the degradation of Tyranno-ZE caused by the oxidation of excess carbon in the fiber at high temperature in air. That is, this result suggests that the h-BN interphase disappeared above, probably as B₂O₃ vapor, and Tyranno fiber was exposed to air at high temperature.

In order to realize long lifetime of ceramic matrix composites at a high temperature in air, ZrSiO₄ were chosen as interphase materials, and the effectiveness of the interphases for ceramic matrix composites was examined. ZMI^F/ZrSiO₄/SiC were exhibited a wood-like destruction during the fracture test. The tensile strengths of ZMI^F/ZrSiO₄/SiC at R.T. and at 1573K in air were equal, and it was about 320MPa.

Fig.6: Tensile strength of SiC matrix composites at 300-1700K in air. Used fiber: TM-S6 --- TM heat-treated in CO gas, SA/BN coat --- SA coated with BN, ZMI/BN coat --- ZMI coated with BN, ZE/BN

Mechanical properties of SiC^F/SiC composites with the SiC-based matrices included oxide particles

The mechanical properties, for example, tensile strength and cyclic fatigue characteristic, of the usual SiC^F/SiC composite are generally insufficient because of the progress of micro cracks at the point of pores, which exist unavoidably in the matrix of SiC^F/SiC composite presenting in as fabricated SiC^F/SiC composite, when it was loaded under high stress.

For the purpose of improving this disadvantage, CMC, of which the matrix was the pyrolyzed precursor polymer including inorganic power particles, was prepared. Enhanced SiC/SiC composite developed by S. L. Bors et al. (Du Pont Lanxide Co.)[7] differs essentially from this composite, because its purpose is the crack seal with matrix dispersed a discontinuous particulate material containing a B₂O₃ glass precursor at high temperature in air.

Fig.7 shows that the tensile strength of the SiC^F/SiC composites at different temperatures in air, which were consisted of Tyranno-ZMI-S6 fiber, carbon-rich SiC interphase and SiC-based matrices including 30mass% BMAS particles and 30mass% ZrSiO₄ particles. Remarkably improved tensile strength of this composite was observed at both room and high temperatures as can be seen in this figure. Particularly, the tensile strength of the specimen with 30wt% ZrSiO₄ particles was about 400MPa at 1673K, and their values are twice usual SiC^F/SiC composite (ZMI-S6^F/C/SiC).

Dynamic tensile strength characteristics of usual SiC^F/C/SiC and SiC^F/C/SiC+ZrSiO₄ were examined in order to investigate the durability of these composites. The test conditions and the results show in Fig.9. In the SiC^F/C/SiC+ZrSiO₄, the rupture strength under the stepwise increasing load from low to high level for long time was the same as the ultimate tensile strength.

From the above, it was found that the addition of BMAS particles and ZrSiO₄ particles to the SiC-based matrix was very effective for improving the strength and the durability of SiC^F/SiC composites at high temperature..

Fig.7: Tensile strength of SiC^F/SiC composites with the carbon-rich SiC interphase and the matrices included oxide particles at high temperatures in air.

CONCLUSION

The chemical composition of SiC-based matrix from precursor polymer and mechanical properties of SiC^F/SiC composites with various Tyranno fibers, with variation of matrices and with unique fiber/matrix interphases have been investigated for developing SiC^F/SiC composites as the excellent thermostructural material. The results can be summarized as:

(1) The SiC-based matrices with variations of C/Si atomic ratio were fabricated by PMS/(PMS+PCS) ratio control. The SiC matrix with near stoichiometry composition was

Test Condition

Specimen : Minicomposite
 Stress : See right figure
 (The stress of 1step is about 10% of ultimate rupture stress.)
 Test Temperature : 1573K
 Atmosphere : Air

Result

Sample	Step Stress (MPa)	Rupture Stress (MPa)	Rupture Time (ks)	Preservation Ratio (%)	Ultimate Rupture Stress
ZMI-Si ^F /C/SiC	18	160	28.8	90	(160)
ZMI-Si ^F /C/SiC+ZrSiO ₄ (30wt%)	34	340	32.4	100	(340)

obtained under the condition of PMS/(PMS+PCS) weight ratio of 0.7 by a simple pyrolysis processing.

(2) Tyranno^F/BN/SiCs, which had h-BN interphase, exhibited an excellent tensile strength below 1600K in air. In particular, SA^F/BN/SiC retained the tensile strength near to that at R.T. even at 1673K in air.

(3) Tyranno-ZMI^F/ZrSiO₄/SiC, which had crystallized ZrSiO₄ interphase, exhibited at 1573K in air the tensile strength equal to that at R.T.

(4) By the addition of BMAS and ZrSiO₄ particles into SiC-based matrix, the tensile strength of Tyranno-ZMI^F/C/SiC was improved greatly. Especially, Tyranno-ZMI^F/C/SiC+ZrSiO₄ with the SiC-based matrix included 30mass% ZrSiO₄ particles have retained 300-400MPa in tensile strength even at 1673K in air.

This paper provides important baseline information about elementary factors to produce attractive SiC^F/SiC composite for thermostructural applications, ex. gas generators. Based on the current results, a new SiC^F/SiC composite with sufficient total performance to meet existing various heat engines design requirements will be produced very soon.

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